

LEGAL BASIS OF PR ACTIVITY: INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. Public Relations (PR) has evolved into a pivotal component of contemporary organizational strategy, serving as a bridge between entities and their stakeholders. The legal framework governing PR activities varies significantly across different jurisdictions, reflecting diverse cultural, political, and legal landscapes. This article explores the legal foundations of PR activities, comparing international and national experiences to highlight both commonalities and unique approaches.

Keywords: public relations (PR), legal framework, international PR standards, national regulations, ethical conduct, transparency, international public relations association (IPRA)

Public Relations (PR) is an essential aspect of modern organizational strategy, playing a critical role in shaping public perception, managing communication, and fostering relationships between organizations and their various stakeholders. As PR activities become increasingly global, understanding the legal frameworks that govern these activities is vital for ensuring compliance, ethical conduct, and effectiveness.

The legal basis of PR activities encompasses a wide array of regulations and guidelines that vary significantly across different countries and regions. These laws and regulations are designed to ensure transparency, protect public interest, and maintain ethical standards in communication practices [3]. At the international level, organizations such as the International Public Relations Association (IPRA) and the Global Alliance for Public Relations and Communication Management set forth principles that guide PR professionals worldwide. These principles advocate for honesty, integrity, and respect for human rights, providing a universal ethical foundation for PR practices.

However, the application and enforcement of PR regulations are heavily influenced by national contexts. In the United States, the legal landscape for PR is shaped by the First Amendment, which safeguards freedom of speech and the press, fostering a relatively open environment for PR activities. Regulatory bodies like the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) also play a crucial role in overseeing advertising and marketing practices to prevent deceptive communication [1].

In contrast, European countries enforce stricter regulations, particularly in light of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which governs data privacy and impacts how PR professionals manage and use personal information. The United Kingdom, through its Public Relations and Communications Association (PRCA), sets rigorous codes of conduct and professional standards, further ensuring ethical PR practices.

In countries with more restrictive media environments, such as China and Russia, PR activities are subject to stringent legal controls reflecting broader governmental oversight over information dissemination. These legal constraints significantly impact how PR professionals operate within these regions, often requiring a careful balance between compliance and effective communication [5].

These examples illustrate the diverse legal environments that PR professionals must navigate. While international guidelines provide a common ethical foundation, national laws reflect unique legal, cultural, and political contexts. Understanding these differences is crucial for PR practitioners, especially when working in multinational settings, to ensure legal compliance and uphold ethical standards.

In summary, the legal basis for PR activities is a multifaceted and dynamic field, influenced by both international principles and national regulations. By examining specific examples, this overview highlights the importance of legal awareness and ethical conduct in the practice of public relations.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the legal basis of PR activity underscores the importance of legal and ethical awareness in the field. As PR continues to evolve in an increasingly globalized world, professionals must stay informed and adaptable to navigate the varied legal landscapes, ensuring that their practices are both legally compliant and ethically sound. This balanced approach is key to sustaining public trust and achieving long-term success in the dynamic field of public relations.

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